

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

S1.1 Block Diagram of Selective Alignment Pipeline

MMSP: Maximal Mappable Safe Prefix

SA: Suffix Array

LCP: Longest Common Prefix

Figure S1: The steps for selective-alignment are described in the form of block diagram. The block wrapped in dotted box is the index building phase, which used for mapping. Mapping undergoes numerous steps including co-mapping and filtering.

S1.2 Synthesized samples with different error rates

To measure the accuracy of selective-alignment in presence of different error rates, we have simulated 3 polyester samples with different error rates of 1%, 2% and 5%. The samples are simulated with 'simulate_experiment_countmat' function in polyester simulator. The input vector for the transcripts is the result of quantification with *Salmon* on experimental sample SRR1215996. The length of simulated reads is set to 100. The 'simulate_experiment_countmat' is used to simulate 9M paired end reads with uniform error model. Three samples with different error rates (1%, 2% and 5%) were simulated from human transcriptome version 'GRCh38.80'. Then reads were mapped to the transcriptome using different methods to compute the quantifications. For *kallisto* and selective-alignment the k-mer value has been set to 25. The results are presented in Tables S1 to S3. The timing performance for *STAR* and *Bowtie2* is the sum of mapping and quantification steps and memory footprint is the max memory footprint of these two steps.

Table S1: Polyester sample with 0.01 error rate. Edit distance in selective-alignment is set to 7.

Method	Spearman	MARD	time (s)	memory (KB)
<i>kallisto</i>	0.94	0.09	80	4036152
<i>Hera</i>	0.95	0.09	113	6763928
selective-alignment	0.96	0.07	107	6649324
<i>STAR</i>	0.96	0.07	354+130	max(8361276, 4851764)
<i>Bowtie2</i>	0.96	0.06	2733+220	max(956348, 9697836)

Table S2: Polyester sample with 0.02 error rate. Edit distance selective-alignment is set to 7.

Method	Spearman	MARD	time (s)	memory (KB)
<i>kallisto</i>	0.93	0.11	89	4031316
<i>Hera</i>	0.94	0.11	111	6760204
selective-alignment	0.95	0.07	131	6671012
<i>STAR</i>	0.96	0.07	394+117	max(8366180, 4847576)
<i>Bowtie2</i>	0.96	0.07	2204+189	max(955068, 9490908)

Table S3: Polyester sample with 0.05 error rate. Edit distance in Selective-alignment is set to 7.

Method	Spearman	MARD	time (s)	memory (KB)
<i>kallisto</i>	0.87	0.18	122	4030068
<i>Hera</i>	0.88	0.26	158	6678432
selective-alignment	0.94	0.12	157	6515100
<i>STAR</i>	0.93	0.10	538+115	max(8366260, 4842184)
<i>Bowtie2</i>	0.95	0.09	1657+149	max(976276, 8434548)

S1.3 Synthetic reads from human transcriptome

We have also explored the performance of different alignment-based and alignment-free methods and selective-alignment on the full human transcriptome. We used the Polyester simulator to generate 30M, 100bp paired-end reads from human transcriptome. The input model (vector of read counts) for Polyester simulation is generated by quantifying sample SRR1216000 from SEQC(MAQC-III) consortium with *Salmon* where reads are mapped by *Bowtie2*. Then for evaluating each mapping method, reads are mapped to the human transcriptome (Ensembl release 80) with each method, and then quantified by *Salmon*, *kallisto* or *Hera*. The Spearman correlation and MARD values for different methods are reported in Table S4. The performance of both alignment-based and alignment-free methods are similar to each other at the transcriptome-wide scale (and when not focusing on adversarial situations). Standard errors for reported numbers are computed by simulating 10 different samples and evaluating standard deviation of all MARD and spearman correlation values.

Transcriptome-wide assessments on synthetic data, like that explored in this experiment, suggest that non-alignment-based methods generally perform well (and similar to alignment-based methods). However, small global differences in quantification accuracy at the transcriptome-wide scale tend to arise from larger differences in the quantification of particular transcripts (e.g., those where accurate mapping tends to be difficult, and where additional modeling fidelity is required to obtain accurate estimates). Moreover, simulations like these, while useful for assessing the internal consistency of different algorithms, tend to present a much cleaner and easier quantification problem than is posed by real data (e.g. there are no sequence differences between the reference and sample apart from a low rate of sequencing error, all expressed transcripts are presented in the indexed reference, and transcript coverage profiles are ideal and near-uniform).

Table S4: Quantification results with different methods for mapping reads on transcriptome wide synthetic data. Again the timing performance for *STAR* and *Bowtie2* is the sum of mapping and quantification steps and memory footprint is the max memory footprint of these two steps.

Method	Spearman(STD)	MARD(STD)	time(s)	memory(KB)
<i>kallisto</i>	0.96 (0.0002)	0.08(0.0005)	76.20	4036090.40
<i>Hera</i>	0.95 (0.0045)	0.09 (0.0071)	54.60	6758412.80
selective-alignment	0.96 (0.0003)	0.08(0.0005)	65.90	6419841.20
<i>STAR</i>	0.95 (0.0002)	0.08 (0.0003)	327.9+113.3	max(8355326.4,4803570.4)
<i>Bowtie2</i>	0.96 (0.0002)	0.08 (0.0003)	2118.7+205.1	max(962611.6,9366696)

S1.4 Performance of different methods, under alternative accuracy metrics, across various mutated reference samples

We observe that *Bowtie2*-based quantification achieves the highest accuracy across all metrics at all error rates, but comes at a significant computational cost. For mutation rates up to ~ 0.03 , selective-alignment, *Bowtie2* and STAR performs very similar, while *Hera* generally outperforms the fully alignment-free approach, but underperforms compared to selective-alignment. For the highest mutation rates, STAR and *Bowtie2* yield a small but consistent advantage over selective-alignment, which, itself, provides a considerable improvement in accuracy compared to the other methods.

Rate 0.03

Rate 0.04

Rate 0.05

S1.5 Scatter plots for results using mutated reference transcriptomes at various rates.

To explore the performance of the different tools while mapping simulated reads to mutated reference transcriptomes in more detail, we provide the scatter plots of read count estimations of every method against the truth for different mutation rates. As demonstrated in the scatter plots, *kallisto* and *Hera* estimations begin to diverge from truth as the mutation rate increases. It's more evident specifically for mutation rates 0.04 and 0.05, while selective-alignment and alignment-based tools stay more correlated with the truth counts.

Rate 0.02

Rate 0.03

Figure S2: With increasing error rate most alignment free methods are more vulnerable to spurious mapping. The performance of selective-alignment matches the accuracy of alignment based methods in all mutation rates expect the last one. Each figure consists of five plots. The first two plots on the upper row represents *kallisto* and *Hera* respectively. The three tools in the bottom row are selective-alignment, *STAR* and *Bowtie2*.

S1.6 Scatter plots for results using various experimental human samples.

The scatter plots for read count estimates are drawn for four tools *kallisto*, *Hera*, selective-alignment and *STAR* against the quantification results from *Bowtie2* and *Salmon*. As discussed in Section 3.2 the selective-alignment is mostly concordant with *Bowtie2*. The lower left box is the plot for selective-alignment.

Sample SRR1215996

Sample SRR1215997

Sample SRR1215998

Sample SRR1215999

Sample SRR1216000

Figure S3: For four different tools scatter plot against *Bowtie2* is shown. selective-alignment and *STAR* shown in the bottom row are more concordant with *Bowtie2* than *kallisto* and *Hera* plotted in top row.